

Deliverable D3

Title

Validation report for the digital twin software, considering requirements of digitisation and industry 4.0, for static, continuous and dynamic force transfer standards including measurement uncertainty determination

EMPIR Grant Agreement number

18SIB08

Project short name

ComTraForce

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Leading partner

Dr. Claudiu Giusca (CU)

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